

Comparison of methane reforming routes for hydrogen production using dielectric barrier discharge plasma-catalysis

Rolando Garcia-Villalva^a, Martí Biset-Peiró^a, Andreina Alarcón^{a,b}, Carmen Bacariza^c,
Sebastián Murcia-López^a, Jordi Guilera^{a,b,*}

^a Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de Les Dones de Negre 1, 08930, Sant Adrià de Besòs, Spain

^b Facultat de Química, Universitat de Barcelona, Martí I Franquès, 1, Barcelona, 08028, Spain

^c Centro de Química Estrutural, Institute of Molecular Sciences, Departamento de Engenharia Química, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Av. Rovisco Pais, 1049 001, Lisboa, Portugal

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ABSTRACT

Methane reforming is an interesting resource for obtaining hydrogen. DBD plasma-catalysis allows a direct use of electricity for methane reforming reactions, such as direct methane reforming (MR), dry methane reforming (DMR) and steam methane reforming (SMR). In this work, the first comprehensive comparison of these three routes for hydrogen production is experimentally and systematically investigated using dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) plasma and various catalyst formulations. Among the three routes, SMR is the most effective, achieving significantly higher methane conversion rates (24 %) and hydrogen content (80 %). DMR produces predominantly syngas mixture, whereas MR yields hydrogen along with other light carbon compounds. In SMR route, the favorable textural properties of Ni/Al₂O₃ are responsible for its high methane conversion rates, while Ni/CeO₂ increases hydrogen content since it favors the water-gas shift reaction, especially at high power inputs. Therefore, SMR using a suitable catalyst stands out as the most feasible reforming route for hydrogen production.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen (H₂) is nowadays primarily obtained from the methane (CH₄) molecule present in the fossil natural gas, constituting about 80 % of the world's hydrogen production. Steam methane reforming (SMR) by thermochemical technology is the predominant for hydrogen production, followed by dry methane reforming (DMR). These processes contribute to the mitigation and utilization of greenhouse gases, such as CH₄ and CO₂ [1–12].

Alternatively, H₂ molecule can be considered as bio-hydrogen if derived from the CH₄ present in biogas, as a biogenic source. Biogas, generated through the anaerobic degradation of organic compounds, typically consists of CH₄ (55–70 %), CO₂ (30–45 %) along with some impurities such as N₂, O₂, CO or H₂S [13,14]. Therefore, biogas can be considered a very important source for by-hydrogen generation, replacing fossil methane [15].

Irrespective of its fossil or biogenic origin, the generation of H₂ requires a large amount of energy for the activation of the stable CH₄ molecule. In this aspect, this energy could be supplied in a controlled,

efficient, and above all, electric manner through plasma discharges [16]. Non-thermal plasma (NTP) is a promising method that significantly reduces the reaction temperature and promotes hydrogen production. NTP consists of applying electricity to a gas stream, where the electrons are accelerated by the applied electric field and, in turn, excite, ionize, and dissociate the gas molecules, developing reactive species and chemical reactions at quasi-ambient pressure and temperature [17].

A challenge of the NTP technology is to assist methane reforming reactions aiming to convert CH₄ and/or CO₂ into products of interest. NTP provides enough energy for chemical reactions in the plasma of active species in the absence or in the presence of a catalyst [17–20]. The plasma-catalysis system can improve the chemical and thermochemical reactions driven by electron interactions, allowing for the achievement of higher conversions and selectivities, while also minimizing carbon deposition [21–25].

Dielectric Barrier Discharge (DBD) represents a form of NTP technology characterized by the presence of two parallel electrodes, with at least one of them being coated with a dielectric material. This configuration is designed to restrict the movement of electric charges and

* Corresponding author. Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC), Jardins de les Dones de Negre 1, 08930, Sant Adrià de Besòs, Spain.

E-mail address: jguilera@irec.cat (J. Guilera).

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achieve their uniform distribution within the discharge zone, thereby preventing the formation of electric arcs. DBD employs a moderate dielectric barrier that reduces operational voltage and enhances electric field discharge for gas molecule interactions. DBD-plasma systems are well-suited for atmospheric operation with precise temperature and pressure control, making them preferable for methane reforming processes [26–28].

The conventional route for large-scale industrial H₂ generation is thermo-catalytic SMR reaction. Thus, SMR seems the most plausible route to be electrified by plasma. In contrast, when producing bio-hydrogen, DMR is the most reported route in literature, as it utilizes all biogenic carbon from biogas [29,30]. Finally, much less reported is methane reforming (MR) [31]. The aforementioned routes have been independently reported using NTP technology. Below, the main findings on plasma-activated processes are briefly described.

The simplest methane reforming, MR (Eq. (1)), is influenced by the presence of plasma, which triggers the decomposition of CH₄ through low-temperature chemical reactions driven by high-energy electron collisions with CH₄ molecules. MR is distinguished by its lack of by-product generation, such as CO or CO₂, or not requiring oxidizing agents [6,18].

On the other hand, DMR (Eq. (2)) converts CH₄ and CO₂ into syngas (H₂ and CO), representing 70% of the products obtained. DMR is the most endothermic of the three reforming reactions. In essence, it demands a higher energy input to occur. Most of the reported catalysts are supported on Al₂O₃ and contain various active phases such as Ni, Mg, Ce, K, Ag, Pt, or bimetallic catalysts among those mentioned. In general, the use of catalysts promotes higher CH₄ conversion and selectivities; but is not as efficient as in analogous CO₂ conversions [32–38].

SMR (Eq. (3)) studies using plasma-catalysis are very rare, in contrast to the classical thermal-catalysis. In these few works [13,39–43], Ni/Al₂O₃ is employed as the catalyst. Most recently, its modification has been investigated by the incorporation of a promoter (Ce and La) and a second metal phase (Au and Ag). It was observed that the plasma temperature ensures a high rate of chemical processes, and the ultraviolet radiation from the plasma prevents the formation of higher hydrocarbons. Furthermore, the presence of water reduces the possibility of carbon generation and deposition on the catalyst surface, thus benefiting the utilization of biogas.

As described, obtaining hydrogen by methane reforming using DBD plasma is feasible using various routes namely: MR, DMR and SMR. However, these three routes have been studied so far independently. In this regard, the simultaneous comparison of three different reactions is pioneering. This work aims to provide a systematic comparison of the three methane reforming routes using promising catalyst formulation, which are also compared without the use of catalyst. The primary objective of this article is to discern the most efficient reforming route and catalyst material by DBD plasma for hydrogen production.

2. Experimental

2.1. Catalyst synthesis

Heterogeneous catalysts were composed by 10 wt % of the active phase, nickel (Ni) and cobalt (Co). On the other hand, cerium oxide (CeO₂), alumina (Al₂O₃) and BEA zeolite were used as the supports. A total of four powder form catalysts were fabricated and sieved (<50 μm), named as Ni/BEA, Co/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂ and Ni/Al₂O₃.

Supports were prepared using a thermal calcination procedure;

namely, cerium (III) nitrate hexahydrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O, 99.5 % purity) was calcinated in an oven at 500 °C for 5 h (1 °C/min) [44], and high-purity alumina hydrates (boehmite, 99.5 % purity) was calcinated at 500 °C for 7 h (5 °C/min). Finally, a commercial NH₄-BEA zeolite (CP814E, Zeolyst International) was calcined in a muffle at 500 °C for 6 h (2 °C/min) in order to obtain its acidic form.

The active phase was incorporated using the wet impregnation method. Both supports were pre-dried at 110 °C overnight. The respective amount of the metal salt (nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate, Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O; 98 % purity) and/or (cobalt (II) nitrate hexahydrate, Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O; 99 % purity) and distilled water were added to the pre-dried support (CeO₂ or Al₂O₃) and mixed at room temperature for 30 min using a rotary evaporator. Then, in the same device, the salt solution was evaporated at a temperature of 80 °C for 2 h under vacuum. After the material impregnation, each catalyst was dried on a furnace at 110 °C overnight. Finally, the catalysts were calcinated at 450 °C for 30 min (1 °C/min).

2.2. Material characterization

Elemental composition of the samples was obtained using a field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM, Zeiss Auriga 60) equipped with a spectrometer of energy dispersive X-ray (EDX, Oxford X-Max). The elemental composition was normalized to the main elements of each catalyst, such as Ni, Co, Ce, Al and O. EDX analysis was expressed as the average of ten individual measurements for each powder sample. This method led to an absolute error of ±1 %.

The skeletal densities of the catalysts were estimated using a helium pycnometer (Ultrapyc 1200e Pycnometer, Quanta-chrome Instruments). Once the equipment reached stability, the helium (He) was passed through the samples at a pressure of 20 psig. Three repetitions were performed to obtain an average of the parameters of density, true volume and standard deviation (±0.01).

Textural properties of the catalysts were obtained from the corresponding N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms at –196 °C using a static automatic volumetric apparatus (TriStar II 3020-micromeritics analyzer). The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) was used to estimate the internal surface area of the material (S_{BET}). On the other hand, the total pore volume and the average pore size were determined by applying the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method to the desorption branch of the isotherms at the value P/P₀ = 0.999.

Temperature-programed reduction (H₂-TPR) and CO-chemisorption were carried out using an automated chemisorption analyzer (Autochem HP-micro-meritics). For H₂-TPR measurements, 0.10 g of each sample was placed inside the reactor, and a flow of 50 NmL/min (12% of H₂ in Ar) was used. The measurements were conducted from room temperature up to 800 °C (10 °C/min). The minimum differences in the concentration of gases that flow into and out of the sample reactor were detected by a thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

For CO chemisorption measurements, 0.10 g of samples were used and reduced to 450 °C with a flow of H₂ (50 mL/min) for 3 h (1 °C/min). CO pulses were introduced periodically until total saturation of the system. The metal dispersion of the catalysts was calculated assuming a CO/Ni and CO/Co stoichiometric ratio equal to 1, an atomic weight for Ni of 58.71 u and Co of 58.93 u, an atomic cross-sectional area for Ni of 0.06 nm² and for Co of 0.07 nm², and a density for Ni of 8.90 g/cm³ and Co of 8.90 g/cm³.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was collected on a Bruker type XRD D8 Advance A25 diffractometer (Cu Kα radiation, λ = 1.54 Å, 40 kV, 40 mA) with a 2θ scan range from 20° to 80° and a step size of 0.05°/3 s. Then, the crystallite size of the samples was calculated by Scherrer equation at 43.28° for NiO and 36.82° for Co₂O₃: D=(Kλ/β·cos θ), where λ represents the wavelength of X-rays, β stands for the full width of the diffraction line at half maximum (FWHM), and θ corresponds to the Bragg angle.

2.3. Reactor configuration

Fig. 1 shows the experimental set-up used in this work. CH₄ (Linde, 99.995 %) and CO₂ (Linde, 99.995 %) gases were fed by using mass flow controllers (Bronkhorst, High-Tech), while steam (Milli-Q; H₂O) was fed using an ultra-high-pressure liquid chromatography pump (LC-20AT, Shimadzu Corporation). The preheater system was composed of a heater (Horst, P/230 V–10 A (2300 W)) and heating blanket (Omega Engineering - heating rope) to guarantee water gas phase at reactor inlet. Temperature in the reactor was not monitored.

The DBD plasma reactor was configured with quartz coaxial tubes as dielectric material. The diameters of the inner and outer tubes were 14 and 18 mm, respectively, both with a thickness of 1 mm. Two stainless steel meshes of approximately 10 mm length were used as internal and external electrodes. Quartz wool was used as a bedding material in the center of the reactor, where the catalyst was located. The plasma was generated by applying a high voltage AC signal (4–9 kVpk, 54 kHz) between the two stainless-steel electrodes, using a plasma controller (PVM500). The instruments were connected to an oscilloscope (PicoScope), monitored using Labview software. Plasma operated in the 10–40 W range for all the experiments. At the reactor outlet, liquid products were condensed, and volumetric gas flow was quantified using a gas bubble flow (Sigma Aldrich, 50 mL tube).

Gas compositions were analyzed using an on-line gas micro-chromatograph (490 Micro GC, Agilent Technologies) equipped with three columns, with a first molecular sieve (CP-Molsieve 5 A, Ar) for H₂ analysis; a second molecular sieve (CP-Molsieve 5 A, He) for CH₄ and CO; and a porous polymer (CP-PoralPlot U, He) for the analysis of CO₂, C₂, C₃ and C₄₊. For simplicity, the sum of C₂H₂, C₂H₄ and C₂H₆ hydrocarbons were grouped as C₂ products, while C₃ is the result of C₃H₆ and C₃H₈ ones.

2.4. Reforming evaluation

MR, DMR and SMR experiments were performed in the DBD plasma reactor using 50 mL/min of gas inlet flow and a molar ratio 1:1 for DRM (CH₄:CO₂) and SMR (CH₄:H₂O). Each reforming process was evaluated with (Co/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂, Ni/Al₂O₃ or Ni/BEA) and without catalyst (NC). 0.30 g of catalyst was used during the plasma-catalysis runs. The catalysts were ex-situ reduced on a tubular oven using a flow (5% H₂ in Ar) of 100 mL/min at 450 °C for 3 h (1 °C/min). Subsequently, they were cooled inside the oven using a similar cooling ramp until reaching room temperature, and directly placed in the reactor. The supports (CeO₂, Al₂O₃ and BEA) were evaluated under the same operating and reaction conditions, and those results were included in the supporting information (SI).

CH₄ (Eq. (4)) and CO₂ (Eq. (5)) conversions were calculated as the ratio between the gas converted and the gas introduced.

$$X_{\text{CH}_4} = \frac{(\text{CH}_4)_{n_{\text{in}}} - (\text{CH}_4)_{n_{\text{out}}}}{(\text{CH}_4)_{n_{\text{in}}}} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

$$X_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{(\text{CO}_2)_{n_{\text{in}}} - (\text{CO}_2)_{n_{\text{out}}}}{(\text{CO}_2)_{n_{\text{in}}}} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

where n_{in} and n_{out} represent the flow rate measured at the inlet and outlet [45]. Carbon balance was met in the range of 95–100 %, as the ratio of the total moles of outlet carbon compounds to the sum of moles of CH₄ and/or CO₂ in the inlet gas. The methane reforming processes can generate carbon from the proposed reactions. Nevertheless, the characteristics of plasma-catalysis operating at atmospheric pressure and low temperatures suggest a minimal in carbon formation due to the high-energy distribution resulting from the synergy of plasma-catalysis, according with the literature [46–49].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the set-up and DBD-plasma reactor configuration used to carry out the three reforming processes.

Product molar fraction (Eq. (6)) was determined by calculating the ratio of specific products with respect to the sum total amount of products.

$$\text{Product molar fraction (\%)} = \frac{n_i \text{ (mol/min)}}{n_{\text{total}} \text{ (mol/min)}} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

where n_i represents the molar fraction of the specific product (H_2 , CO , CO_2 , C_2 , C_3), and n_{total} the sum of all products.

Energy barrier (E_a , kJ/mol) was obtained according to the method present in the literature, an analogous method to the Arrhenius equation [50–52]. In this case, energy barrier indicates the dependence of the rate of generation of a specific product on the applied power.

$$r_{(x)} = A \cdot e^{\frac{-E_a}{R \cdot T}} \cdot P \quad (7)$$

where $r_{(x)}$ is the reaction velocity ($x = \text{H}_2\text{--C}_{2-3}$; mol x /(s · gcat)), A is the pre-exponential factor, F_{total} is the total flow rate of feed gas (mmol/s), and P is the applied power (W).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization

A summary of physicochemical properties of the supports and catalysts is presented in Table 1. EDX analysis confirmed the presence of 10 ± 1 wt% nickel or cobalt metal, aligning with nominal quantities. One of the most notable differences is in terms of surface area, with Al_2O_3 catalyst exhibiting a S_{BET} three times superior to that of the CeO_2 ones. Similarly, pore volume of Al_2O_3 -based materials was significantly higher than CeO_2 -based ones. In addition, BEA catalyst exhibited a significantly higher BET surface area compared to the other oxides, attributed to its three-dimensional structure with molecular-sized pores and inter-crystallite spaces acting as mesopores. The skeletal density of the catalysts was higher than that from the supports due to the higher density of Ni and Co metals compared to the initial supports. Among these, CeO_2 skeletal density was almost double than the collected for Al_2O_3 support.

H_2 -TPR profiles of the catalyst are shown in Fig. 2. With the incorporation of active phase (compared with Fig. S1), new peaks at temperatures lower than 450°C were identified and associated to the phase changes of $\text{NiO} \rightarrow \text{Ni}^0$ for Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Co}_2\text{O}_3 \rightarrow \text{CoO} \rightarrow \text{Co}^0$ for Co/CeO_2 [53,54]. Compared to Ni/CeO_2 ($170\text{--}350^\circ\text{C}$), the reduction peaks of the $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ were detected at higher temperatures ($360\text{--}480^\circ\text{C}$). Ni/BEA presented peaks ascribed to the reduction of NiO located in the external surface of the zeolite ($300\text{--}400^\circ\text{C}$), while reduction processes ($500\text{--}600^\circ\text{C}$) are due to NiO located in the mesopores of this zeolite [55]. This indicates that metal-support interactions are stronger in Al_2O_3 and BEA-based catalyst, while the implementation of CeO_2 as support is favorable as lower reduction temperatures are required to obtain metallic phases in these catalysts.

XRD diffractograms are shown in Fig. 3, and it confirmed the

Fig. 2. H_2 -TPR profiles of the catalysts.

Fig. 3. XRD profiles of the calcined catalyst and supports.

presence of the metal oxide material corresponding to the active phases (NiO and Co_2O_3) and those of the metal oxide (CeO_2 , Al_2O_3) or zeolite (BEA) supports. In the case of $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalyst, as suggested by the high reduction temperatures and uncompleted processes in H_2 -TPR, the presence of a fraction of Ni as NiAl_2O_4 cannot be excluded. However, the proximity with Al_2O_3 and NiO peaks difficulties the attributions [56]. Additionally, the application of Scherrer's equation for crystalline size estimation revealed that the NiO crystallite size in $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (8.57 nm) was roughly half than that found in Ni/CeO_2 (16.26 nm). Furthermore, smaller NiO crystallites (6.91 nm) were found in Ni/BEA , probably due to the encapsulation effect in the zeolite's mesopores. In the same direction, CO -chemisorption analysis of the reduced catalysts revealed a

Table 1
Physicochemical properties of the samples.

Sample	Elemental composition		Skeletal density (g/mL)	BET area, S_{BET} (m^2/g)	Pore volume (cm^3/g)	Pore diameter (nm)	Crystallite size of metal oxide-active phase di (nm)	Metal dispersion (%)	Metallic surface area of sample (m^2/g)
	Ni	Co							
BEA	–	–	2.1	648	0.6	12.7	–	–	–
CeO_2	–	–	5.4	66	0.2	12.5	–	–	–
Al_2O_3	–	–	3.1	219	0.5	7.8	–	–	–
Ni/BEA	10	–	2.5	556	0.5	13.6	6.9	2.2	1.4
Co/CeO_2	–	9	6.2	48	0.2	12.3	24.4	0.1	0.1
Ni/CeO_2	10	–	5.4	57	0.2	12.1	16.3	0.8	0.5
$\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$	11	–	3.3	165	0.4	8.7	8.6	1.4	1.1

higher metallic surface for Ni/BEA and Ni/Al₂O₃. These results indicate that these catalysts have more active sites and better dispersion of the metal, which is attributed to the greater surface area available for the incorporation of the active phase. The identification of well-dispersed nickel species is well aligned with the presence of small NiO crystallites strongly interacting with the Al₂O₃ support, as identified by XRD and H₂-TPR measurements, and in accordance with the literature [57].

3.2. Non-catalytic plasma reforming

Fig. 4 shows the CH₄ conversion for each reforming route without catalyst. As seen, a higher applied power led to higher CH₄ conversion rates in all scenarios due to the greater intensity of the electric field, which in turn promoted greater molecular collisions and dissociations. Another fact to highlight is the quite high CH₄ conversions achieved in non-catalytic plasma experiments. Experiments were performed at equal total flow rate in all reforming routes (50 mL/min), so that, when CO₂ or H₂O were present, CH₄ flow rates were consequently lower (25 mL/min). As a result, CH₄ conversion was positively affected, despite having a significantly higher reaction enthalpy. DMR achieved better CH₄ conversions with an increasing trend compared to MR method. Furthermore, the interaction of CH₄ and H₂O significantly improved CH₄ conversion compared to other reforming methods, which was observed consistently in each experiment. Although there were increasing trends in all scenarios, stabilization occurred from 30 W onwards. Specifically, SMR exhibited a 39 % increase over DMR and twofold to MR at the highest applied power.

The decomposition of both CH₄ and CO₂ in the presence of plasma results in the formation of different reaction products due to the recombination of radicals formed during plasma exposure. The distinguishing factor between them lies in the energy threshold or limit required to trigger these distinct reactions. For CH₄, this threshold is 9 eV, whereas for CO₂, it is 11 eV [35,58,59]. On the other hand, the H₂O molecule has O–H bonds with an energy limit of 7 eV [60], even lower than CH₄, so the induced electric field will cause dissociation and excitation of the molecules faster and at lower powers. In addition, due to these phenomena, radicals such as H• and •OH were produced, which were essential for a greater production of H₂. As a result, given that the activation energy threshold for the H₂O reactant was lower compared to that of CH₄ and CO₂, the interaction between CH₄ and H₂O leads to an enhancement in CH₄ conversion.

Fig. 5 shows the different products generated and their molar fraction based on the CH₄ reforming process employed. Something distinctive was that the product molar fraction remains constant for each route, even if the power is gradually increased, which is different from conventional thermal methods [61,62].

For MR, the primary product obtained was H₂ in all the experiments

Fig. 4. CH₄ conversion by different reforming routes without catalyst.

Fig. 5. Product molar fraction by different reforming routes without catalyst.

in accordance with Eq. (1), followed by short chain hydrocarbons formed by carbon coupling. The direct plasma CH₄ reforming achieved a H₂ of 69 %, and a large C₂ and C₃ hydrocarbons molar fractions (31 %), approximately. In the case of SMR, the introduction of steam led to an additional 4 % increase of H₂ content compared to MR, whereas the production of CO and CO₂ was insignificant. On the other hand, the main products from DMR were H₂ and CO, i.e., syngas. In contrast to MR, the introduction of CO₂ as an oxygen source result in a noteworthy quantity of CO being produced in each experimental run, in accordance with Eq. (2). The molar fraction varied resulting in a decrease of 53 and 56 % for H₂ and C₂, respectively, with respect to MR due to the increase of CO molar fraction.

3.3. Plasma-catalysis reforming

The introduction of a catalytic material was evaluated in the three routes. Fig. 6 depicts CH₄ conversions concerning different supports and catalysts in SMR, as the most active route, while the rest of the results (i. e., MR, DMR) are provided in the supporting information (SI). As seen, BEA and Al₂O₃ support achieved similar conversions rate at all applied powers. In contrast, CeO₂ exhibited lower performance.

Upon introducing the active phase to the support, the catalysts displayed varied performances. Ni/Al₂O₃ consistently achieved the highest conversions at all power levels, indicating that the incorporation of the metal promotes the reaction. In contrast, CeO₂-based catalysts exhibited a performance decline after metal incorporation. Similarly, Ni/BEA experienced lower conversion than BEA support. The lower activities exhibited by CeO₂ and BEA-based catalysts could be potentially ascribed

Fig. 6. CH₄ conversions by SMR with supports and catalysts.

to the lower residence time after the incorporation of material inside the reactive zone (Table S1). The interplay between plasma and catalysis influences reactive species formation, concentration, and residence time. These hypotheses were in accordance with the literature [63–68].

Fig. 7 shows the product molar fraction of the most active catalyst (Ni/Al₂O₃), both with and without the metallic phase. Al₂O₃ exhibited no significant changes in selectivities when compared to the previous Fig. 5. However, with the addition of the metallic phase, Ni/Al₂O₃ achieved 7 % improvement in H₂ production, while the molar fraction of C₂ and C₃ hydrocarbons decreased by 23 and 21 %, respectively, within the 30–40 W range. Variations were observed for CO and CO₂, but their production remained low. Ni/Al₂O₃ exhibited the highest level of activity, also presenting strong affinity for C₂ and C₃ at all power levels used. This behavior can be attributed to its higher metal surface area and metal dispersion, in agreement with CO-chemisorption. This indicates that this catalyst has the potential to produce a higher quantity of desirable derivatives, compounds, or hydrocarbons, essentially promoting carbon coupling.

Experiments using solely H₂O feed and Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst showed no substantial formation of reaction products despite the increased of the power input. Therefore, the interaction of CH₄ and H₂O as a couple could be consider promoting conversions and products selectivity, a behavior that will be studied through the production mechanism in future research.

Fig. 8 depicts the products molar fraction of BEA and Ni/BEA, where it can be observed that with the BEA support, there were not significant changes compared to NC. Ni/BEA did exhibit a shift in its product molar fraction as power increased, with both H₂ and CO₂ production increasing. The rate of H₂ increase was 2 and 4 % for the 20–30 W and 30–40 W ranges, respectively. On the other hand, the production of C₂ decreased with the presence of the active phase at each power level, and furthermore, the production of CO and C₃ was negligible due to the increased presence of H₂ and CO₂.

Fig. 9 shows the performance of CeO₂ as a support and its behavior when metallic phases such as Co and Ni were introduced. As previously discussed, the single support did not significantly alter the selectivities with respect to NC conditions, but the addition of a suitable active phase had positive and strong impact on the product molar fraction. Indeed, Co/CeO₂ displayed consistent H₂ production between 20 and 40 W, with a 7 % increase when compared to CeO₂. Additionally, CO₂ increased ninefold within the same power range.

Ni/CeO₂ achieved a predominant production towards H₂, with more than 80%. Ni/CeO₂ led to an enhancement in H₂ molar fraction of 7, 15 and 12 % when compared to Co/CeO₂, CeO₂ and NC, respectively. It was interesting to find that Ni/CeO₂ was much more selective towards the

Fig. 7. Product molar fraction by SMR with Al₂O₃-based and catalyst.

Fig. 8. Product molar fraction by SMR with BEA-based and catalyst.

Fig. 9. Product molar fraction by SMR with CeO₂-based and catalyst.

production of CO₂ than CO in all applied powers. Therefore, CO₂ obtained a notable increase in its production, with a 45 % with respect to Co/CeO₂ and a remarkable fourteen-fold increase for CeO₂. However, as a consequence of this substantial rise in CO₂, both C₂ and C₃ exhibited low productivities.

This outcome was a consequence of Ni/CeO₂ favoring the water-gas shift (WGS) reaction (Eq. (8)), and therefore, the total amount of produced H₂ was higher. As a result, it can be concluded that Ni/CeO₂ was the only catalytic system able to complete the overall SMR (Eq. (9)), which is very interesting if the desired product is H₂. In contrast, Ni/CeO₂ exhibited low conversions, suggesting that this catalyst is involved in catalyzing two reactions, while Ni/Al₂O₃ appears to catalyze only Eq. (3) reaction.

Therefore, it can be claimed that CeO₂-based systems have notable strength to promote the WGS reaction due to the creation of oxygen vacancies on the surface, significantly influencing the adsorption and subsequent reactions of various adsorbates. On the other hand, even if plasma or support packing demonstrates substantial CH₄ conversions at lower temperatures, these conversions could tend to decrease at elevated temperatures. The synergy of plasma-catalysis could be stronger at temperatures where the catalyst becomes active, suggesting the

involvement of surface reactions, in accordance with the literature [64, 69,70].

In terms of H₂ production rates (Fig. 10), Ni/CeO₂ catalyst exhibited the highest performance, exceeding Ni/Al₂O₃, Ni/BEA, and Co/CeO₂ by 8, 28, and 64 %, respectively. In general, when steam, an additional H₂ source, is introduced in catalyst-containing experiment, a positive impact was observed (compared with Fig. S6 and Fig. S13). When CeO₂ is combined with an optimal metal, such as nickel, it promotes the associated redox processes of the active phase. CeO₂ support allows the activation of its catalytic phase by storing and releasing oxygen, which provides an additional advantage in the formation of the WGS reaction.

3.4. Energy barrier

An analysis of energy barrier by means of the correlation between reaction rate and applied power was additionally performed to understand how this factor impacts the conversion of CH₄, as well as the production of H₂ and other byproducts. According to Table 2, significant changes were identified between E_{a,H2} and E_{a,C2-3} for Ni/BEA and Ni/CeO₂ from SMR. Lower energy required to initiate the reaction and generate products was preferentially derived from SMR when compared to the other reforming reactions (Table S3).

In the case of SMR and with respect to Ni/CeO₂ and Ni/BEA, a large difference between E_{a,H2} and E_{a,C2-3} was detected, which indicates that the selectivity was highly dependent on the applied power. Consequently, both catalyst exhibited elevated E_{a,H2} indicating the involvement of reactions described by Eq. (8) and Eq. (9) during plasma processing. As a result, both produced a significant amount of CO₂, as shown in Figs. 8 and 9. In this aspect, an increase of the reactor power is beneficial for both conversion and selectivity to hydrogen in Ni/CeO₂. In contrast, this process optimization cannot be achieved from Ni/Al₂O₃ because E_{a,H2} was very similar to E_{a,C2-3}.

In general, plasma-catalysis perform more effectively at higher power levels. This phenomenon arises due to the utilization of the catalytic material, which leads to enhanced CH₄ conversions, consequently resulting in elevated E_a requirements. High activation energies estimated for the dissociation of CH₄ agreed with other reported works [71–73].

These findings are very decisive for the future design of plasma-catalysis reforming reactors. Optimizing the reactor configuration could result in an increased gas residence time at the reaction site, and an increase in the generated power, leading to improvements in both conversions and selectivities. The possible temperature generated by thermal losses at higher powers might indicate the potential to establish an adiabatic system for efficient energy utilization [74]. Moreover, conducting stability tests in future research would be intriguing to examine the catalyst's behavior and ascertain the occurrence of a substantial amount of coke deposition. In addition to engineering optimization, it would be intriguing to explore potential catalysts with a defined geometry, such as pellets, and investigate whether these characteristic influences achieving higher CH₄ conversions and selectivities. This could be attributed to a better intrusion of the electric field across the entire catalyst surface.

4. Conclusions

Non-thermal Plasma by Dielectric Barrier Discharge was used to evaluate the hydrogen production from three reforming routes, such as methane reforming (MR), dry methane reforming (DRM), and steam methane reforming (SMR). The performance comparison of the reforming routes was carried out in the absence (NC) and presence of catalysts based on Co/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂, Ni/Al₂O₃, and Ni/BEA.

Plasma-catalysis revealed that the mere exposure of methane to plasma resulted in a significant production of hydrogen. Moreover, the addition of CO₂ as a reactant enhanced CH₄ conversion and led to the main product being syngas. Beyond this, the most important finding is

Fig. 10. H₂ and C_xH_y products comparison by steam methane reforming at 40 W.

Table 2

Energy barrier (kJ/mol) for SMR.

NC	Ni/BEA	Co/CeO ₂	Ni/CeO ₂	Ni/Al ₂ O ₃
H ₂ generation				
21.94	27.77	28.13	32.48	24.39
C ₂₋₃ generation				
21.70	15.16	20.58	22.18	23.90

that the combination of CH₄ and H₂O surpassed expectations in terms of CH₄ and hydrogen production, along with other valuable products. This is attributed to the reaction, coupled with an optimal catalyst, facilitating the water-gas shift (WGS) reaction.

The main conclusions are summarized as follows:

- MR was characterized by its low methane conversion (12 %) and its product molar fraction mainly towards H₂ (73 %), with a slighter inclination towards C₂₋₃ (27 %).
- DMR achieved a positive impact on its methane conversion (19 %); however, the introduction of CO₂ leads to a decrease in hydrogen production (48 %) due to the predominant formation of CO (34 %), with a smaller proportion of C₂₋₃ (18 %).
- SMR stands as the prevailing reforming route, achieving the highest methane conversion (24 %) and highest hydrogen yield (80 %). Furthermore, it consistently enhances hydrogen production across all scenarios, facilitating the generation of valuable byproducts.

The synergy of plasma-catalysis favored hydrogen production, and Ni/Al₂O₃ emerged as the most active catalyst, attributed to its high available metallic area. On the other hand, Ni/CeO₂ was identified as the most selective for hydrogen production due to the Ni–CeO_{2-x} interaction, making it the only catalytic system capable of completing the overall SMR.

The substantial difference in results between E_{a,H2} and E_{a,C2-3} suggests the alternative to improve the maximum selectivity and methane conversions by increasing the power. Additionally, optimizing the reactor to increase residence time could contribute to improvements in these crucial parameters.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.02.161>.

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